

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KARTHIKA ASHOKAN bearing USN 6SU20FS803 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NITHIN S bearing USN 6SU20FS804 has completed his/her internship at Rural police Station Mangalore, in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

Dean
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